

QUOTIENTS OF PALINDROMIC AND ANTIPALINDROMIC NUMBERS

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Abstract

A natural number N is said to be *palindromic* if its binary representation reads the same forwards and backwards. In this paper we study the quotients of two palindromic numbers and answer some basic questions about the resulting sets of integers and rational numbers. For example, we show that the following problem is algorithmically decidable: given an integer N , determine if we can write $N = A/B$ for palindromic numbers A and B . Given that N is representable, we find a bound on the size of the numerator of the smallest representation. We prove that the set of unrepresentable integers has positive lower asymptotic density in \mathbb{N} . We also obtain similar results for quotients of antipalindromic numbers (those for which the first half of the binary representation is the reverse complement of the second half). We also provide examples, numerical data, and a number of intriguing conjectures and open problems.

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1. Introduction

Let $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ denote the natural numbers, and let $P, Q \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be two given subsets. Define the *quotient set*

$$P/Q = \{p/q : p \in P, q \in Q - \{0\}\}.$$

In the special case where $P = Q$, the set P/P is also known as a *ratio set* in the literature [5, 6, 14, 17, 20, 21, 19, 25, 26, 27, 31, 32]. Given P and Q , six classical problems of number theory are as follows:

1. What is the topological closure of P/Q in \mathbb{R}^+ ? In particular, is P/Q dense in the positive reals \mathbb{R}^+ ?
2. Consider the following computational problem: given an integer N , is $N \in P/Q$? Is it algorithmically decidable? Efficiently decidable?
3. Suppose $N \in P/Q$. What are good upper and lower bounds on the size of the smallest denominator in a representation $N = A/B$ for $A \in P, B \in Q$?
4. What are the integers in P/Q ? Are there infinitely many? Are there infinitely many integers not so representable? What are the lower and upper asymptotic densities of representable and unrepresentable integers in \mathbb{N} ? (The lower asymptotic density of a set $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |S \cap \{1, 2, \dots, n\}|$ and the upper asymptotic density is $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |S \cap \{1, 2, \dots, n\}|$.)
5. Given that an integer N belongs to P/Q , how many such representations are there?
6. What are the rational numbers in P/Q ?

These are, in general, very difficult questions to answer; for some sets P, Q , we can even prove that some variations are undecidable [9, Thm. 5]. Let us look at some examples of each of these problems in the literature.

1.1. Problem 1: Denseness

As an example of Problem 1, Sierpiński [27, p. 165] proved that if $P = Q = \mathcal{P} = \{2, 3, 5, \dots\}$, the set of prime numbers, then P/Q is dense in \mathbb{R}^+ . Also see [12, 29]. More generally, there is a criterion originally due to Narkiewicz and Šalát [22], as follows:

Theorem 1. *Suppose $P = \{a_1, a_2, \dots\} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ with $a_i < a_{i+1}$ for all i . If*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n+1}/a_n = 1,$$

then P/P is dense in the positive reals.

As another example, one of the basic steps in the proof of Cobham’s famous theorem [8] is the following observation: if $P_k := \{k^i : i \geq 0\}$ is the set of powers of an integer $k \geq 2$, then P_k/P_ℓ is dense in \mathbb{R}^+ if and only if k and $\ell \geq 2$ are multiplicatively independent. Also see [10, Prop. 9].

Let $s_q(n)$ be the sum of the base- q digits of n . Madritsch and Stoll [18] showed that if P_1 and P_2 are polynomials with integer coefficients, of distinct degrees, such that $P_1(\mathbb{N}), P_2(\mathbb{N}) \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, then the sequence of quotients $(s_q(P_1(n))/s_q(P_2(n)))_{n \geq 1}$ is dense in \mathbb{R}^+ .

Brown et al. [4] proved that if we take $P = Q$ to be the set of integers whose base- k representation starts with 1, then P/Q is dense in the positive reals if and only if $k \in \{2, 3, 4\}$.

Recently, Athreya, Reznick, and Tyson [2] solved Problem 1 for $P = Q = C$, the Cantor numbers (the natural numbers having no digit “1” in their base-3 representation).

1.2. Problem 2: Deciding if an Integer Is Representable

Let S_1, S_2 be sets of natural numbers and L_1, L_2 the corresponding sets of their canonical base- b representations. If L_1 and L_2 are both regular languages (that is, recognized by finite automata), then we can decide whether a given $N \in S_1/S_2$ in $O(N)$ time.

To see this, build an automaton M that accepts, in parallel, the base- b representation of two natural numbers (A, B) if $A = BN$, starting with the least significant digits. For this we only need N states, to keep track of the possible carries. Now use the direct product construction to intersect M with L_1 in the first component (corresponding to A) and L_2 in the second component (corresponding to B), getting an automaton M' . If some final state M' is reachable from the start, then N has a representation; otherwise it does not. This gives an algorithm running in $O(N)$ time to decide whether $N \in S_1/S_2$. (The implicit constant depends on the size of the finite automata recognizing L_1 and L_2 .)

Of course, is not necessary to construct the entire automaton. We can use a queue-based algorithm to do breadth-first search on the underlying directed graph of the automaton, implicitly. If N is representable, we can often find a representation A/B in much less than $O(N)$ time.

1.3. Problem 3: Size of the Smallest Denominator in a Representation

Continuing the example of regular languages, if N has a representation as A/B , then $A = b^{O(N)}$. This follows from the fact that the automaton M' constructed there has t states, so if M' accepts an input, it must accept an input of length at most $t - 1$. The corresponding integer is then at most $b^{t-1} - 1$, and $t = O(N)$.

1.4. Problem 4: Characterizing Representable Integers

In 1987, Loxton and van der Poorten [16] considered the set L of integers that can be represented in base 4 using just the digits 0, 1, and -1 . They showed that every odd integer can be represented as the quotient of two elements of L .

Recall the definition of the Cantor numbers C from Section 1.1. The problem of completely characterizing the ratio set $V = \mathbb{N} \cap C/C$ was proposed by Richard Guy [11, Section F31] and is still unsolved. Let

$$D = \{N : \exists i \geq 1 \text{ such that } N \equiv 2 \cdot 3^{i-1} \pmod{3^i}\} \\ = \{2, 5, 6, 8, 11, 14, 15, 17, 18, 20, \dots\}.$$

By considering the numerator and denominator modulo 3^i , it is easy to see that if $N \in D$, then $N \notin V$. Let

$$E = \mathbb{N} \cap \bigcup_{i \geq 0} [(3/2) \cdot 3^i, 2 \cdot 3^i] = \{2, 5, 6, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, \dots\}.$$

By considering the first few bits in the base-3 representation of numerator and denominator (or using the results in [2]), it is easy to see that if $N \in E$, then $N \notin V$. It is tempting to conjecture that $V = \mathbb{N} - (D \cup E)$, but this is false. Define $F := \mathbb{N} - (V \cup D \cup E)$. Then, using the algorithm given above for Problem 3, Sajed Haque and the fourth author of this article found that

$$\{529, 592, 601, 616, 5368, 50281, 4072741, 4074361, 4088941, 4245688\} \subset F.$$

We do not know if there are infinitely many such examples. It seems at least possible that numbers of the form $621 \cdot 3^{4k} - 20$ might all belong to F .

A related conjecture was made by Selfridge and Lacampagne [16, §7]. If we let $B = \{1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 11, 13, 14, 16, 20, 22, \dots\}$ be the set of natural numbers having no 0 in their balanced ternary representation, then they conjectured that every $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ belongs to B/B . However, we found the counterexamples

$$\{247, 277, 967, 977, 1211, 1219, 1895, 1937, 1951, 1961, 2183, 2191, \\ 2911, 2921, 3029, 3641, 3649\},$$

the first of which was also found by Coppersmith [11, Section F31]. It seems likely that there are infinitely many such counterexamples, but we have no proof.

For a different example, let $U = \{2^{k+1} + i : k \geq 1, 1 \leq i \leq 2^{k-1}\}$. Šalát [25] observed that $U/U \cap \mathbb{N}$ has lower density $1/4$ and upper density $2/5$.

1.5. Problem 5: Counting Number of Representations

Consider $S = \{1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, \dots\}$, the set of integers that can be written as the sum of two squares of natural numbers. Then it follows from Fermat’s classical two-square theorem that $S/S \cap \mathbb{N} = S$. Hence every $N \in S/S$ has infinitely many representations of the form $N = A/B$ with $A, B \in S$.

1.6. Problem 6: Which Rationals Are Representable?

As an example, Sierpiński observed [27, p. 254] that if we take $P = Q = \{\varphi(n) : n \geq 1\}$, the range of Euler’s totient function, then P/Q contains every positive rational number.

On the other hand, it is a nice exercise in elementary number theory to show that every non-negative rational number belongs to \mathbb{N}/T , where $T = \{(2^i - 1)2^j : i \geq 1, j \geq 0\}$. See [24, Example 7].

Define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} &= \{0, 3, 5, 6, \dots\} = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : t(n) = 0\} \\ \mathcal{O} &= \{1, 2, 4, 7, \dots\} = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : t(n) = 1\}, \end{aligned}$$

where t is the Thue-Morse sequence. Stoll [30] showed that for odd natural numbers $p > q$ there are integers $n_1, n_2 < p$ such that $t(n_1p), t(n_1q) \in \mathcal{E}$, and $t(n_2p), t(n_2q) \in \mathcal{O}$. Since $t(2n) = t(n)$, we immediately get that \mathcal{E}/\mathcal{E} and \mathcal{O}/\mathcal{O} both contain all positive rational numbers.

2. Palindromic and Antipalindromic Numbers

Now that we have motivated the study of the properties of P/Q for sets P, Q , we turn to considering Problems 1–6 above for $P = Q$ in a novel context: the palindromic and antipalindromic numbers. These two classes have previously been studied by number theorists; see, e.g., [3, 7, 23].

We say that a natural number is *palindromic* if its base- b representation is a palindrome (reads the same forwards and backwards). For base 2, the palindromic numbers $\text{PAL} = \{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 15, 17, \dots\}$ form sequence A006995 in the *On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences* (OEIS).

Analogously, we say that a natural number is *antipalindromic* if its base-2 representation is of even length, and the second half is the reverse complement of the first half. For example, 52 (which is 110100 in binary) is antipalindromic. The antipalindromic numbers $\text{APAL} = \{2, 10, 12, 38, 42, 52, 56, \dots\}$ form sequence A035928 in the OEIS. This can be generalized to base b by demanding that if a is a digit in the first half of a number’s representation, and a' is the corresponding digit in the reverse of the second half, then $a + a' = b - 1$.

As it turns out, the study of the palindromic and antipalindromic numbers is particularly amenable to tools from automata theory and formal languages. These tools have previously been used to solve other kinds of number theory problems (see, e.g., [23]).

Our principal interest in this paper is base 2, although nearly everything we say can be generalized to other bases. We let $Q_{\text{pal}} = \mathbb{N} \cap \text{PAL}/\text{PAL}$, the integers

representable as quotients of palindromic numbers, and $Q_{\text{apal}} = \mathbb{N} \cap \text{APAL}/\text{APAL}$, the integers representable as quotients of antipalindromic numbers.

Throughout the paper we must distinguish between an integer and its base- k representation. For $n \geq 1$, define $(n)_k$ to be the string of digits representing n in base k , starting with the most significant digit, which must be nonzero. If w is a string of digits over the alphabet $\Sigma_k = \{0, 1, \dots, k - 1\}$, then by $[w]_k$ we mean the integer represented by w in base k . Thus, for example, $(43)_2 = 101011$ and $[101011]_2 = 43$. The representation of 0 is ϵ , the empty string.

For a string x , by x^n we mean the string $\overbrace{xx \cdots x}^n$. In some cases (for example, an equality such as $1^4 = 1111$) there could be ambiguity between this notation and the ordinary notation for powers of integers, but the context should make it clear which interpretation is meant.

We use the notation \bar{a} to denote the binary complement of the bit a : $\bar{0} = 1$ and $\bar{1} = 0$. This can be extended to strings w in the obvious way. Another extension is that if we are working over base b , then we can define $\bar{a} = b - 1 - a$. Here the choice of b should be clear from the context.

The *Hamming distance* $h(x, w)$ between two identical-length strings, x and w , is defined to be the number of positions on which x and w differ.

2.1. Denseness

Theorem 2. *The ratio set PAL/PAL is dense in the positive reals.*

Proof. Let $\alpha > 0$ be a real number that we want to approximate as the quotient of two palindromic natural numbers. Without loss of generality, we can assume $\alpha \leq 1$ (otherwise, we represent the reciprocal $1/\alpha$). Let $k \geq 0$ be an integer such that $\frac{1}{2} < 2^k \alpha \leq 1$, and set $\beta = 2^k \alpha$.

Fix a positive integer n . We now approximate β by forming a palindrome from the first n bits of the binary expansion of β (duplicating the bits, then reversing and appending them), and dividing by the palindromic number $B = 2^{2n+k} + 1$. More formally, let $\gamma = \lfloor 2^n \beta \rfloor$, and define $A = [(\gamma)_2 (\gamma)_2^R]_2$. Then $A/B \approx \alpha$, and it remains to see how good this approximation is.

Clearly $\gamma \leq A/2^n < \gamma + 1$. Therefore

$$2^n \beta - 1 < \lfloor 2^n \beta \rfloor = \gamma \leq A/2^n < \gamma + 1 = \lfloor 2^n \beta \rfloor + 1 \leq 2^n \beta + 1.$$

Multiplying through by $2^n/B$ gives

$$\frac{2^{2n} \beta - 2^n}{2^{2n+k} + 1} < \frac{A}{B} < \frac{2^{2n} \beta + 2^n}{2^{2n+k} + 1},$$

or equivalently,

$$\frac{\beta - 2^{-n}}{2^k + 2^{-2n}} < \frac{A}{B} < \frac{\beta + 2^{-n}}{2^k + 2^{-2n}} < \frac{\beta}{2^k} + 2^{-n-k}. \tag{1}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\beta - 2^{-n}}{2^k + 2^{-2n}} &= \frac{\beta - 2^{-n}}{2^k} \left(\frac{1}{1 + 2^{-2n-k}} \right) \\ &> \frac{\beta - 2^{-n} - 2^{-2n-k}\beta + 2^{-3n-k}}{2^k} \\ &> \frac{\beta - 2^{-n} - 2^{-2n-k}}{2^k}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the fact that $\beta < 1$ and the estimate $1/(1 + x) > 1 - x$. Substituting in Eq. (1), we see that

$$\alpha - 2^{-n-k} - 2^{-2n-2k} < \frac{A}{B} < \alpha + 2^{-n-k}.$$

Hence, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the quotient of palindromes A/B gets as close as desired to α . □

Remark 1. We could have also proved Theorem 2 using the criterion in Theorem 1. More general results follow from the multidimensional results of Leonetti and Sanna [15] and Antony et al. [1].

2.2. Testing if N Is the Quotient of Palindromic Numbers

We now turn to the question of deciding, given a natural number N , whether there exist palindromes A, B such that $N = A/B$. Since a positive number must be odd for its base-2 representation to be a palindrome, it is clear that only odd integers are representable.

The set Q_{pal}

$$1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 27, 31, 33, 39, \dots$$

of positive integers having such a representation is sequence A305468 in the OEIS.

The sequence

$$23, 25, 29, 35, 37, 41, 47, 49, 59, \dots$$

of odd positive integers having no representation as the quotient of palindromic numbers is sequence A305469 in the OEIS.

Evidently, if there exist such A, B we can find one through a brute-force search, so for the moment we focus on how we might establish that there is no such solution. We describe three algorithms: a heuristic algorithm that does not always terminate; a rigorous algorithm based on context-free languages; and finally, a fast rigorous algorithm based on deterministic finite automata.

2.2.1. A Heuristic Algorithm

There is a fast and relatively simple heuristic method to solve this problem that works in many cases, but is not guaranteed to terminate. If it does terminate, the answer it gives is guaranteed to be correct. We describe it now. Suppose we are considering a candidate T for the first k bits of B . Since $A = BN$, these k bits of B determine all the possibilities for the first k bits of A .

On the other hand, the first k bits of B determine the last k bits of B . By considering the equation $A = BN$ modulo 2^k , the last k bits of A are also completely determined. Hence the first k bits of A are completely determined, and must match one of the possibilities in the preceding paragraph. If they do not, we have ruled out T as the possibility for the first k bits of A .

We now do a breadth-first search over the tree of possible prefixes of B . The hope is that we either find a solution, or are able to rule out all possibilities for the solution of $A/B = N$. This will be the case if the following heuristic principle holds:

Heuristic Principle 1. If there is no solution in palindromes A, B to the equation $A/B = N$, then this fact can be proved by examining all possible k -bit prefixes of B for some fixed integer k (which might depend on N).

We illustrate the basic idea for $N = 35$. Suppose A, B are palindromes with $A/B = 35$. Then the first three bits of B are either 100, 101, 110, 111.

Let us assume the first three bits are 100. Then, since $A = 35B$, we see that the first three bits of A are either 100 or 101. On the other hand the last three bits of B are 001, so from $A = 35B$ we see the last three bits of A are 011. So the first three bits of A are 110, contradicting what we found earlier.

Similar contradictions occur for the other three possibilities, so we have proved that there is no solution in palindromic numbers to the equation $A/B = 35$.

Using our heuristic algorithm, we were able to determine the representability of all odd $N \leq 2000$. The data for $N \leq 239$ is given in Table 1. Here k denotes the length of the largest bit strings that were needed to prove that $N = A/B$ has no solutions in palindromic numbers.

Unfortunately, the heuristic principle does not hold in all cases. We found six examples less than 20000 for which a failure to terminate occurs. They are summarized in Table 2. For each entry we have $N \cdot [rs^n(s^R)^n r^R]_2 = [tu^{n-i}vwv^R(u^R)^{n-i}t^R]_2$ for $n \geq 2$, and furthermore $\text{pald}(w) = d$. Here $\text{pald}(w) = h(w, w^R)$, the Hamming distance between w and w^R . For these numbers there is an infinite sequence $(f(n))$ of palindromic numbers whose product with N is “almost” palindromic, and furthermore the first bit position where this product differs from being a palindrome is located arbitrarily far in (and hence will never be detected by an algorithm that focuses only on fixed-size prefixes).

N	A	B	k	N	A	B	k	N	A	B	k
1	1	1		81	—	—	3	161	—	—	3
3	3	1		83	3735	45		163	7335	45	
5	5	1		85	85	1		165	165	1	
7	7	1		87	—	—	4	167	—	—	5
9	9	1		89	—	—	3	169	—	—	3
11	33	3		91	273	3		171	513	3	
13	65	5		93	93	1		173	5709	33	
15	15	1		95	2565	27		175	—	—	8
17	17	1		97	—	—	3	177	—	—	3
19	513	27		99	99	1		179	11277	63	
21	21	1		101	—	—	5	181	16833	93	
23	—	—	4	103	—	—	7	183	—	—	4
25	—	—	3	105	—	—	6	185	—	—	3
27	27	1		107	107	1		187	561	3	
29	—	—	8	109	2289	21		189	189	1	
31	31	1		111	—	—	6	191	29223	153	
33	33	1		113	—	—	4	193	—	—	3
35	—	—	3	115	—	—	3	195	195	1	
37	—	—	6	117	585	5		197	—	—	6
39	195	5		119	119	1		199	—	—	9
41	—	—	3	121	11253	93		201	—	—	3
43	129	3		123	—	—	3	203	1421	7	
45	45	1		125	—	—	5	205	1025	5	
47	—	—	6	127	127	1		207	—	—	6
49	—	—	3	129	129	1		209	—	—	4
51	51	1		131	—	—	3	211	633	3	
53	3339	63		133	3591	27		213	54315	255	
55	165	3		135	—	—	4	215	645	3	
57	513	9		137	—	—	8	217	—	—	8
59	—	—	3	139	—	—	3	219	219	1	
61	427	7		141	—	—	6	221	1105	5	
63	63	1		143	2145	15		223	2965677	13299	
65	65	1		145	—	—	4	225	—	—	4
67	—	—	3	147	—	—	6	227	—	—	3
69	—	—	7	149	5887437	39513		229	3435	15	
71	54315	765		151	1057	7		231	231	1	
73	73	1		153	153	1		233	59415	255	
75	—	—	4	155	—	—	7	235	—	—	3
77	231	3		157	471	3		237	—	—	6
79	888987	11253		159	3339	21		239	717	3	

Table 1: Results of the heuristic algorithm for odd $N \leq 239$

N	r	s	t	u	v	w	i	d
2551	ϵ	10100010000	1100100	11110001011	111	0010110001011	1	12
14765	ϵ	111011110110	1101011111000	110000010111	1100000101101	1011010110	2	8
15247	ϵ	11001101110011001000	10111111100	00100011001101110011	0010001	011100000011000101	1	10
17093	ϵ	110111001000	11100110000	110010001101	ϵ	0110000000010101	1	6
19277	11	000010001110011110111000110	1110010010000101	1001101101001101100100101100	10011011010011	1100111100100	1	8
19831	ϵ	11101010111100	1000111000110	00100000011111	0010000001111	0111010111111010101	2	12

Table 2: Some N for which the heuristic principle fails.

Let us verify the claim for $N = 2551$. For the given r, s, t, u, v, w we have

$$[s^n (s^R)^n]_2 = 1296 \cdot 2^{11n} \cdot \frac{2^{11n} - 1}{2^{11} - 1} + 69 \cdot \frac{2^{11n} - 1}{2^{11} - 1}$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} [tu^{n-1}vwv^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R]_2 &= [t]_2 \cdot 2^{|u^{n-1}vwv^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R|} \\ &\quad + [u]_2 \cdot 2^{|vwv^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R|} \frac{2^{(n-1)|u|} - 1}{2^{|u|} - 1} \\ &\quad + [v]_2 \cdot 2^{|wv^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R|} + [w]_2 \cdot 2^{|v^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R|} \\ &\quad + [v^R]_2 \cdot 2^{|(u^R)^{n-1}t^R|} \\ &\quad + [u^R]_2 \cdot 2^{|t^R|} \frac{2^{(n-1)|u^R|} - 1}{2^{|u^R|} - 1} + [t^R] \\ &= 100 \cdot 2^{11(n-1)+3+13+3+11(n-1)+7} \\ &\quad + 1931 \cdot 2^{3+13+3+11(n-1)+7} \frac{2^{11(n-1)} - 1}{2^{11} - 1} \\ &\quad + 7 \cdot 2^{13+3+11(n-1)+7} + 1419 \cdot 2^{3+11(n-1)+7} \\ &\quad + 7 \cdot 2^{11(n-1)+7} + 1679 \cdot 2^7 \frac{2^{11(n-1)} - 1}{2^{11} - 1} + 19. \end{aligned}$$

The expression for $[s^n (s^R)^n]_2$ simplifies to

$$\frac{1296}{2^{11} - 1} \cdot 2^{22n} - \frac{1227}{2^{11} - 1} \cdot 2^{11n},$$

while the expression for $[tu^{n-1}vwv^R(u^R)^{n-1}t^R]_2$ simplifies to

$$\frac{3306096}{2^{11} - 1} \cdot 2^{22n} - \frac{3130077}{2^{11} - 1} \cdot 2^{11n}.$$

It is now easily verified that the second is 2551 times the first.

Conjecture 1. There are infinitely many natural numbers N for which the heuristic algorithm fails to terminate.

2.2.2. A Provable Decision Procedure

In contrast to the fast method presented in Section 2.2.1, in this section we describe another technique that provides a provable decision procedure. This method is based on formal language theory.

Here is a brief sketch of the idea: first, given N , we construct a pushdown automaton (PDA) M_N that, on input A and B expressed in binary, and read in parallel, determines if A and B are both palindromes and if $A = BN$. Next, we convert M_N to an equivalent context-free grammar (CFG) G_N . Finally, we use a standard decision procedure for context-free grammars to decide if G_N generates any string, and if so, to find the shortest string generated by G_N .

However, there are some complications. While determining if A is palindromic with a PDA is easy, making the same determination for A and B simultaneously (when they are of different lengths) is harder. To align A and B around their center, we multiply B by 2^k for some appropriate power of 2. Thus, instead of checking whether $A = BN$, we are actually checking if $2^k A = BN$. Now there are four separate cases to examine, depending on the parity of the length of $(A)_2$ and $(B)_2$.

Our solution consists of five parts:

- **ConstructPDA(N)**: on input a positive integer N , constructs four PDAs that accept the base-2 representation of all (A, B) in parallel such that $A = BN$ and both A and B are palindromes. This PDA has $O(N^{3/2})$ states, where $O(N)$ states are used to keep track of the multiplication by N , and an additional multiplicative factor of $O(N^{1/2})$ states required to keep track of the symbols required to “line up” the binary representation of A with B .
- **CanonicalPDA(M)**: on input M returns a new PDA M' that is in Sipser normal form: it has at most one final state, empties the stack before accepting, and each transition either pushes exactly one symbol onto the stack or pops one off.
- **PDA-to-Grammar(M)**: takes a PDA M in Sipser normal form and returns an equivalent CFG G using the algorithm in [28]. This blows up the number of states by at most a cubic factor, so the size of the grammar is $O(N^{9/2})$.
- **Remove-Useless-Symbols(G)**: takes a CFG G and removes useless symbols (both variables and terminals) following the algorithm in Hopcroft and Ullman [13]. If nothing is left, we know $L(G)$ is the empty set.
- **Shortest-String-Generated(G)**: given that the CFG G generates at least one string, this routine returns the shortest string (or perhaps strings) generated by G , using dynamic programming.

Using these ideas we were able to prove

Theorem 3. *There exists an algorithm to determine if N can be written as the quotient of palindromic numbers that runs in $O(N^{9/2})$ time.*

This method was programmed up by the first author in 2019, and with it we were able to determine the solvability of $N = A/B$ in palindromes for all odd numbers up to 600. Unfortunately, it was too slow to resolve the cases we were interested in (such as $N = 2551$, which the heuristic algorithm could not solve), so we turned to another method described in the next section.

2.2.3. A Different Provable Decision Procedure Based on Finite Automata

We developed another method that is based on finite automata (instead of pushdown automata). Of course, finite automata cannot recognize palindromes, so we have to be a bit more clever.

Let N and k be integers. The case of the representability of $N = A/B$ with A, B palindromes in base k is easy to decide in the cases where $N < k$ or $k \mid N$, so we assume neither of these holds.

We construct a nondeterministic finite automaton $M_{N,k}$ to check whether N can be expressed as the quotient of palindromic numbers in base k . This automaton accepts certain pairs of strings a and b , from which we derive integers A and B , where $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ are palindromes and $A/B = N$. This is accomplished by interpreting the input each a and b as half of a palindrome $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$, respectively, and then verifying the equation $A = BN$. The automaton verifies the equation from both the left-hand and right-hand halves of the digits of $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ simultaneously. From the size of the constructed $M_{N,k}$ we can also obtain a bound on the maximum size of A .

Verifying a Multiplication with a System of Equations

To verify the equation $A = B \cdot N$ we compare $N \cdot B$ to A digit by digit. Let $(A)_k = A_i A_{i-1} \cdots A_1$ and $(B)_k = B_j B_{j-1} \cdots B_1$. We begin by checking

$$A_1 = (N \cdot B_1) \bmod k.$$

This leaves a carry to contribute to the next equation

$$c_1 = \frac{N \cdot B_1 - A_1}{k}.$$

We call these c_ℓ values the *carries*. We then subsequently verify each equation

$$A_\ell = (N \cdot B_\ell + c_{\ell-1}) \bmod k$$

for $\ell \in \{2, 3, \dots, |(A)_k|\}$. When $\ell > |(B)_k|$ we continue with $B_\ell = 0$. At each step we get a new equation

$$c_\ell = \frac{N \cdot B_\ell + c_{\ell-1} - A_\ell}{k}$$

for the next step. If at the end of the process we have that $c_i = 0$, then all the equations are valid and indeed $A = N \cdot B$.

We can also obtain a bound on the size of c_ℓ . This contributes to the bound on the size of $M_{N,k}$. We have

$$c_\ell \leq \frac{(k-1) \cdot N + c_{\ell-1} - 0}{k}.$$

Since the carry starts at 0, c_1 includes $c_0 = 0$ so we have that $c_1 \leq \frac{k-1}{k} \cdot N < N$. We can then assume for the sake of induction that $c_{\ell-1} < N$ and get that

$$\begin{aligned} c_\ell = \frac{N \cdot B_\ell + c_{\ell-1} - A_\ell}{k} &\leq \frac{(k-1) \cdot N + c_{\ell-1} - 0}{k} < \frac{(k-1) \cdot N + N}{k} \\ &< \frac{k \cdot N - N + N}{k} \\ &< \frac{k \cdot N}{k} \\ &< N, \end{aligned}$$

as $A_\ell \geq 0$ and $B_\ell \leq k-1$. We can use the fact that c_ℓ is bounded by N to constrain the states we have to consider in $M_{N,k}$. Any state with a left carry larger than or equal to N cannot lead to an accepting state, so we can safely omit it.

The automaton $M_{N,k}$ simultaneously checks the equations starting with $\ell = 1$ in ascending order and the equations starting with $\ell = i$ in descending order. The ascending equations have a carry computed as previously described. The descending equations start with the assumption that $c_i = 0$ and compute the required preceding carry value that would result in the equation being satisfied. We compute $c_{\ell-1}$ from the relation

$$c_{\ell-1} = k \cdot c_\ell - N \cdot B_\ell + A_\ell.$$

The states of the automaton keep track of the value of the largest index carry computed from the right and the smallest index carry computed from the left. An accepting state is one where the top and bottom carries are equal. This implies that each equation is satisfied from $\ell = 1$ up to $\ell = i$.

Palindromes as Input to an Automaton

There are two main challenges regarding the input specification when trying to design an automaton that verifies an equation and ensures that the inputs are palindromes. The first challenge is that it is impossible to recognize a palindrome

with a finite automaton. To remedy this issue we take, as input, *half* of a palindrome and implicitly determine the other half. A naive approach is to interpret the input pair $\langle a, b \rangle$ as referring to the equation $[aa^R]_k = [bb^R]_k \cdot N$.

This means that all even-length palindromes have an associated string that is a valid input to our automaton. However, this does not cover the case of odd-length palindromes. Therefore, on input $\langle a, b \rangle$, the automaton $M_{N,k}$ simultaneously checks each equation $[a\sigma_a a^R]_k = [b\sigma_b b^R]_k \cdot N$ where $\sigma_a, \sigma_b \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \Sigma_k$. If any of the equations are valid, then the automaton accepts the input.

The second challenge is that the strings $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ have, in general, different lengths. Furthermore, the difference in length between them could be either the floor or the ceiling of $\log_k N$. To accommodate both possibilities, $M_{N,k}$ begins by nondeterministically guessing the difference in length between $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$. Since $|(A)_k| > |(B)_k|$, it follows that $|a| \geq |b|$. If $|(N)_k| = 2$, then it is possible that there is a satisfying a and b where $|a| = |b|$. However, in general we need to pad b to provide it as input to the automaton simultaneously with a . We use X as a padding character to indicate the end of input for b . We format the input a and b as $\langle a, b \rangle \in (\Sigma_k \times (\Sigma_k \cup \{X\}))^*$. The automaton $M_{N,k}$ rejects any input not of the form $\langle a, b \rangle = xy$ where $x \in (\Sigma_k \times \Sigma_k)^*$ and $y \in (\Sigma_k \times \{X\})^*$. Additionally, the automaton rejects an input that begins with either $a[1]$ or $b[1]$ being zero. This would result in a palindrome representing a number that would not be a palindrome in canonical representation.

Checking Equations for the First Component of the Input

This section describes the states that read the component of the input composed of symbols in $\Sigma_k \times \Sigma_k$. The automaton is able to directly check the equations and compute the carries for the right-hand side, since each input from $\Sigma_k \times \Sigma_k$ contains all the information for one set of equations. The first symbol of $\langle a, b \rangle$ is $(a[1], b[1])$. Since $A_1 = a[1]$ and $B_1 = b[1]$, $(a[1], b[1])$ has all the information required for the equations

$$A_1 = (N \cdot B_1) \bmod k \quad \text{and} \quad c_1 = \frac{N \cdot B_1 - A_1}{k}.$$

Afterwards, the automaton saves the carry for the next equation. On receiving each input $(a[\ell], b[\ell]) = (A_\ell, B_\ell)$, the automaton is able to check the equation

$$A_\ell = (N \cdot B_\ell + c_{\ell-1}) \bmod k$$

and compute

$$c_\ell = \frac{N \cdot B_\ell + c_{\ell-1} - A_\ell}{k}.$$

Therefore, the only information that $M_{N,k}$ must preserve between states in order to verify these equations is the current value of the carry. We call this saved value the *right carry*.

The left-hand side requires more careful handling. The automaton does not verify the equations on the left side. Instead it asserts that they are valid, and computes the carry required from the right to satisfy the current step. Since $(A)_k$ is a palindrome in canonical notation and there is a difference in length between it and $(B)_k$, we must have $A_i = a[1]$ and $B_i = 0$. Using $c_i = 0$ from the assumption of satisfaction, $M_{N,k}$ computes c_{i-1} with the equation

$$c_{i-1} = k \cdot c_i - N \cdot B_i + A_i = k \cdot 0 - N \cdot 0 + A_i = A_i.$$

The automaton preserves the carry for the next equation and we call this saved value the *left carry*. The automaton proceeds with calculating $c_{\ell-1}$ with $A_\ell = a[i - \ell + 1]$, $B_\ell = 0$, and c_ℓ from the previous step with the equation

$$c_{\ell-1} = k \cdot c_\ell - N \cdot B_\ell + A_\ell = k \cdot c_\ell - N \cdot 0 + A_\ell = k \cdot c_\ell + A_\ell.$$

The equation using $a[\ell]$ to compute the left carry is computed concurrently with the corresponding equation on the right-hand side to compute the right carry that also uses $a[\ell]$. (This event is upon reading $(a[\ell], b[\ell])$). We call this the *loading phase*.

The left-hand side continues as described until trying to compute c_{j-1} . At this step, $M_{N,k}$ needs $B_j = b[1]$ along with $a[i - j + 1]$ to compute

$$c_{j-1} = k \cdot c_j - N \cdot B_j + A_j.$$

In order to compute an equation requiring information contained in different input symbols the automaton saves some additional information beyond the two carries. After the first input symbol $(a[1], b[1])$ is read and the right and left carries are computed, $M_{N,k}$ preserves $b[1]$. The automaton keeps $b[1]$ until it has to compute c_{j-1} and at that point discards it, as it will not be needed for any other calculations. Similarly, to compute c_{j-2} , $M_{N,k}$ needs $b[2]$ which gets preserved after reading $(a[2], b[2])$ and discarded at the step computing c_{j-2} . Each time that an $(a[\ell], b[\ell])$ is read the $b[\ell]$ must be saved for a later equation. This process of using, discarding, and then subsequently replacing a saved symbol continues while the input symbols are of the form $(a[\ell], b[\ell])$. (This means that this phase continues until we have seen all of b .) We call the section of computation where $M_{N,k}$ consumes and discards saved symbols while still saving new ones the *shifting phase*.

The number of symbols of b that need to be saved is the difference in length between $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$. As stated previously, this difference can vary between the floor and ceiling of $\log_k N$. To accommodate both possibilities, $M_{N,k}$ nondeterministically assumes that the difference is a fixed value m and the loading phase saves that many symbols of b before starting to consume and replace them in the shifting phase. We call the currently saved section of b the *queue of saved symbols*.

Each state of $M_{N,k}$ is therefore identified by the at most m symbols saved, the integer m itself, the left and right carries, and what phase the automaton is in.

The automaton also has a special start state, with an ϵ transition to the two states with no symbols saved, left and right carries set to 0, and each possibility for m . For all other states, the automaton has a transition to the resulting state when the equations are checked, carries updated, and saved symbols updated as per the input on the transition and the current status as given by the original state. If the associated equation on the right-hand side is not verified, or it results in a carry larger than N , then the transition is omitted. The loading stage is characterized by having less than m saved symbols and the shifting phase having exactly m saved symbols that it cycles through.

Checking Equations for the Second Component of the Input

Once $M_{N,k}$ has seen all of the input b , the input changes to being of the form $(a[\ell], X)$. We call this final section of processing the *unloading phase*. Any transition with an input of the form $(a[\ell], X)$ pushes the automaton directly into the unloading phase. This can lead to not having m saved symbols in the queue of saved symbols despite having read all of b . If this occurs, $M_{N,k}$ implicitly pads the front of the queue of saved symbols with enough zeroes to have m saved symbols. At this point the automaton has all the digits of $(B)_k$ (except σ_b), and has yet to examine the middle section of $(A)_k$ that corresponds to the remainder of a . At this point, when the automaton reads a symbol $(a[\ell], X)$, it represents $a[\ell]$ which is both the leftmost and rightmost digit of the unexamined middle of $(A)_k$. This middle section lines up with the queue of saved symbols to supply the b symbols that are no longer coming from the input.

The automaton must now contend with the possibility that $(B)_k$ has odd length and there may be a symbol of $(B)_k$ not given in b . It nondeterministically decides what the central symbol $\sigma_b \in \Sigma_k \cup \{\epsilon\}$ is for $(B)_k$. If $\sigma_b \neq \epsilon$, then it proceeds using the input $a[\ell]$ as the symbol from $(A)_k$ for both the left and right side equations. The automaton uses the chosen symbol as the $(B)_k$ symbol for the right-hand side equations since we have already processed the entire right-hand side of $(B)_k$. The left-hand side, as usual, pops the first in symbol in the queue of saved symbols but does not add anything else to the queue since there is no new $b[\ell]$. The left and right carries are updated as usual and the automaton continues with a reduced queue of saved symbols. If $M_{N,k}$ decides that $\sigma_b = \epsilon$, then it skips the step described in this paragraph and proceeds directly with the subsequent steps.

At this point, $M_{N,k}$ consumes both ends of the queue of saved symbols to compute the usual equations for the left-hand and right-hand sides with the input $a[\ell]$. This proceeds, consuming two symbols of the queue of saved symbols each time. Once the automaton has less than 2 symbols left, there are two remaining cases. If there are 0 saved symbols remaining and the left and right carries are equal, then the automaton accepts the input. In this case, the entire series of equations are satisfied and the input represents a valid $A/B = N$ with $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ palindromes. Alternatively,

if the automaton has one saved symbol left, then this is the case where $(A)_k$ has an odd number of symbols. If there is an assignment for the middle symbol σ_a that results in the carries being equal, then the automaton accepts the input.

Algorithm Implementation

We implemented an algorithm for computing the desired A and B for a given N and base k in Python. We build the automaton as described and afterwards run Dijkstra’s algorithm using the symbols of B as edge weights to get the shortest B from the start to accept state. Computing the automaton is $O(k^2N^3)$ as it has $O(kN^3)$ states with $O(k)$ transitions out of each state. Given the size of the automaton and a binary heap handling the Dijkstra’s algorithm, our algorithm runs in $O(k^2N^3 \log(k^2N^3))$. The existence of A and B can be shown in $O(k^2N^3)$ with a simple breadth first search of the automaton for the accept state but due to the nondeterminism and variability in the difference of lengths, it cannot guarantee a minimal example.

The code is available at

<https://github.com/josephmeleshko/Palindrome-Ratio-Set-Automata-Generator> .

This guaranteed decision algorithm can prove that there are no solutions for a variety of integers that the heuristic algorithm fails to determine. For example, our algorithm was able to prove that there are no solutions to the equation $N = A/B$ for $N \in \{2551, 14765, 15247, 17093, 19277, 19831\}$.

Let $Q_{\text{pal}} = \{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 27, 31, \dots\}$ be the set of integers representable as the quotient of palindromic numbers. With this code we computed the data in Table 3 showing the distribution of elements of Q_{pal} according to the number of bits.

i	$ Q_{\text{pal}} \cap [2^{i-1}, 2^i) $
1	1
2	1
3	2
4	4
5	5
6	10
7	17
8	33
9	55
10	98
11	165
12	309
13	571
14	985

Table 3: Number of i -bit numbers representable as the quotient of palindromes

Remark 2. Curve-fitting this numerical data to an equation of the form ca^n suggests that perhaps roughly $0.33 \cdot 1.77^i$ i -bit numbers are representable.

We can easily prove the following lower bound on the number of representable i -bit numbers.

Theorem 4. *There are $\Omega(2^{i/2})$ i -bit integers representable as the quotient of palindromic numbers.*

Proof. Every i -bit palindromic number N can be written as $N/1$, and there are $\Omega(2^{i/2})$ of them. \square

Remark 3. Letting $Q_{\text{pal}}(x)$ be the number of integers less than or equal to x in PAL/PAL, we see that the previous result shows that $Q_{\text{pal}}(x) = \Omega(x^{1/2})$.

Even the following seems hard to prove.

Conjecture 2. The set of integers representable as quotients of palindromic numbers is of zero density.

2.3. Size of Smallest Denominator of a Representation as Quotient of Palindromes

The sequence

$$1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 5, 1, 1, 27, 1, 1, 1, 1, 5, 3, 1, \dots$$

of the minimal size of denominators B for those N having a representation A/B as a quotient of palindromes forms sequence A305470 in the OEIS. See Table 1.

Suppose $N = A/B$ for palindromic numbers A, B . We can use our algorithm based on finite automata to upper bound the size of the numerator and denominator of the smallest such representation using the following simple idea.

Proposition 1. *If an NFA of t states accepts the base- k representation of the first halves of strings $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ for palindromic numbers A, B such that $N = A/B$, then $A, B < k^{2t-1}$.*

Proof. By the pigeonhole principle applied to the sequence of states traversed by an input, if an NFA of t states accepts at least one string, then it must accept a string of length at most $t - 1$. Hence if we have an NFA as given in the hypothesis, it must accept at least one pair of inputs in parallel of length less than t . Thus $|(A)_k|, |(B)_k| \leq 2(t - 1) + 1 = 2t - 1$, and so $A, B < k^{2t-1}$. \square

A naive bound on the size of the automata $M_{N,k}$ shows that each of the three phases has unique states that are characterized by one of two maximum numbers

of saved symbols s , up to $\lceil \log_k N \rceil$ saved symbols each taking one of k values, and two carries each ranging from 0 to $N - 1$. This means there are at most

$$3 \cdot 2 \cdot k^{\lceil \log_k(N) \rceil} \cdot N^2 \leq 6 \cdot k \cdot N \cdot N^2 \in O(k \cdot N^3)$$

states in $M_{N,k}$.

More strongly, we have that the loading phase takes at most $\lceil \log_k N \rceil$ transitions since the automaton adds one symbol to the queue of saved symbols at a time. The shifting phase takes at most $k^{\lceil \log_k(N) \rceil} \cdot N^2$ transitions since the automaton at worst goes through every state once. The unloading phase takes at most $\left\lceil \frac{\lceil \log_k N \rceil}{2} \right\rceil = \left\lceil \frac{\log_k N}{2} \right\rceil$ transitions since the automaton removes two symbols from the queue of saved symbols at a time. However, the unloading phase can also require an extra check that implicitly uses the central symbol of $(A)_k$ if $\lceil \log_k N \rceil$ is even and both $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ have an extra central symbol.

Since each transition adds two digits to A and the unloading phase can may implicitly use one additional symbol from $(A)_k$, we have therefore shown:

Theorem 5. *If there exists an A and B such that $(A)_k$ and $(B)_k$ are palindromes and $A/B = N$, then for the smallest A ,*

$$|(A)_k| \leq 2 \cdot \left(\lceil \log_k N \rceil + k^{\lceil \log_k N \rceil} \cdot N^2 + \left\lceil \frac{\log_k N}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 1.$$

Record-setting values of the smallest representation A, B (in terms of B) are given in Table 4.

N	A	B
1	1	1
11	33	3
13	65	5
19	513	27
53	3339	63
71	54315	765
79	888987	11253
149	5887437	39513
319	224725611	704469
575	147606740625	256707375
1823	394070635302093	216166009491
2597	96342506397593044197	37097615093412801
5155	324903223321029232798074465	63026813447338357477803
10627	9300753824529071312360470246068903	875200322247960036921094405389
22331	79377444895975693055708664734623129867563975	3554585325152285748766677029001080554725

Table 4: Record-setting values of smallest representation $N = A/B$ in palindromic numbers.

Conjecture 3. Let $P(N)$ be the smallest natural number b such that $N = a/b$ is solvable for palindromes a, b , and 0 otherwise. Then $B(N) \neq O(q(N))$ for all polynomials q .

The available numerical data suggest that perhaps the smallest denominator of a solution, when one exists, is bounded by $N^{O(\log N)}$.

2.4. Infinitely Many Integers with No Representation

Since $2^n + 1$ is a palindrome for every $n \geq 1$, it is clear that infinitely many integers belong to Q_{pal} . We now prove that there are infinitely many odd integers in the complement $\mathbb{N} - Q_{\text{pal}}$.

Theorem 6. *There are infinitely many odd positive integers N for which there is no solution to $N = A/B$ in palindromes A, B .*

Proof. We prove that if $5 \cdot 2^k < N < 6 \cdot 2^k$ and $N \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, then N has no representation.

We prove this by considering the four possibilities for the first three bits of A :

- $A = 100 \dots 001$. Then $A \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ and $4 \cdot 2^{j+3} < A < 5 \cdot 2^{j+3}$ for some j . Hence $\frac{2}{3} \cdot 2^{j-k} < B < 2^{j-k}$, i.e., B starts with 101, 110 or 111. Therefore B ends with 101, 011 or 111, i.e., $B \equiv 5, 3$ or $7 \pmod{8}$, i.e., $A \equiv 5, 3$ or $7 \pmod{8}$, a contradiction.
- $A = 101 \dots 101$. Then $A \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and $5 \cdot 2^{j+3} < A < 6 \cdot 2^{j+3}$ for some j . Hence $\frac{5}{6} \cdot 2^{j-k} < B < \frac{6}{5} \cdot 2^{j-k}$, i.e., B starts with 110, 111 or 100. Therefore B ends with 011, 111 or 001, i.e., $B \equiv 3, 7$ or $1 \pmod{8}$, i.e., $A \equiv 3, 7$ or $1 \pmod{8}$, a contradiction.
- $A = 110 \dots 011$. Then $A \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $6 \cdot 2^{j+3} < A < 7 \cdot 2^{j+3}$ for some j . Hence $2^{j-k} < B < \frac{7}{5} \cdot 2^{j-k}$, i.e., B starts with 100 or 101. Therefore B ends with 001 or 101, i.e., $B \equiv 1$ or $5 \pmod{8}$, i.e., $A \equiv 1$ or $5 \pmod{8}$, a contradiction.
- $A = 111 \dots 111$. Then $A \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ and $7 \cdot 2^{j+3} < A < 8 \cdot 2^{j+3}$ for some j . Hence $\frac{7}{6} \cdot 2^{j-k} < B < \frac{8}{5} \cdot 2^{j-k}$, i.e., B starts with 100, 101 or 110. Therefore B ends with 001, 101 or 011, i.e., $B \equiv 1, 5$ or $3 \pmod{8}$, i.e., $A \equiv 1, 5$ or $3 \pmod{8}$, a contradiction.

□

In fact, we have proved something more:

Corollary 1. *The set of unrepresentable N has positive lower asymptotic density in the natural numbers.*

Proof. From the result above, a number N is unrepresentable if $N \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ and the first three bits of N in base 2 are 101. Let us count the number $f(x)$ of integers less than or equal to x satisfying these two conditions. Clearly $f(x)/x$ achieves a

local minimum when $x = 5 \cdot 2^n$. In this case $f(x) = 2^{n-3} - 1$. It follows that $\liminf_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x)/x = 1/40$. \square

Remark 4. This bound $1/40$ for the lower asymptotic density can easily be improved by considering other intervals.

2.5. Infinitely Many Different Representations

Theorem 7. *Suppose there is one solution in palindromes A, B to the equation $N = A/B$. Then there are infinitely many solutions.*

Proof. Suppose there is one solution $N = A/B$. Let $d = |(A)_2| - |(B)_2|$. For each $i \geq 0$ define $A_i = [(A)_2 0^i (A)_2]_2$ and $B_i = [(B)_2 0^{i+d} (B)_2]_2$. Then A_i and B_i are clearly palindromic numbers, and $N = A_i/B_i$. \square

2.6. Rational Solutions to $p/q = A/B$ in Palindromes

Our automaton method, discussed in Section 2.2.3, can be modified to get a solution A, B in palindromes where $A/B = p/q$ for integers p/q . Instead of computing $N \cdot B = A$, the automaton computes $p \cdot B = q \cdot A$. For simplicity, we assume that $p > q$ as $p = q$ is trivial and if $p < q$ then solutions to p/q can be derived from the solutions to q/p .

The structure of the automaton is similar but each state has a few modifications. In place of the right carry, we have a carry $c_{A,\ell}$ for A and a carry $c_{B,\ell}$ for B . At each step, the automaton verifies

$$q \cdot A_\ell + c_{A,\ell-1} = (p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1}) \pmod k.$$

Let m be the remainder of $p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1}$ divided by k . The automaton then computes

$$c_{A,\ell} = \frac{q \cdot A_\ell + c_{A,\ell-1} - m}{k}$$

and

$$c_{B,\ell} = \frac{p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1} - m}{k}.$$

We get familiar bounds on the size of the carries, $0 \leq c_{A,\ell} < q$ and $0 \leq c_{B,\ell} < p$.

There is still just a single left carry, but it has to implicitly track the left carry for both A and B . To accomplish this, it tracks the difference between the left carry of B and the left carry of A . Let $c_\ell = c_{B,\ell} - c_{A,\ell}$. We can then derive an equation

for computing $c_{\ell-1}$ from c_ℓ .

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_\ell &= c_{B,\ell} - c_{A,\ell} \\
 c_\ell &= \frac{p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1} - m}{k} - \frac{q \cdot A_\ell + c_{A,\ell-1} - m}{k} \\
 k \cdot c_\ell &= p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1} - m - q \cdot A_\ell - c_{A,\ell-1} + m \\
 k \cdot c_\ell &= p \cdot B_\ell + c_{B,\ell-1} - q \cdot A_\ell - c_{A,\ell-1} \\
 k \cdot c_\ell - p \cdot B_\ell + q \cdot A_\ell &= c_{B,\ell-1} - c_{A,\ell-1} \\
 k \cdot c_\ell - p \cdot B_\ell + q \cdot A_\ell &= c_{\ell-1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

From the bounds on $c_{A,\ell}$ and $c_{B,\ell}$ we get that $-q < c_\ell < p$.

The remaining structure is essentially identical. An accepting state is one where the left carry is equal to the difference of the two right carries. (With the nondeterminism around the middle symbols handled as usual.) The automaton nondeterministically chooses the difference in size of A and B to be either the floor or ceiling of $\log_k \frac{p}{q}$. Since $1 < p/q < k$ can be a valid input, A and B could have the same length. However, this only simplifies the construction as we ignore the loading and unloading phase entirely since all of the symbols in the equations line up perfectly.

Given the constraints on all the information we track, (and $p > q$), there are at most

$$6 \cdot (p + q - 1) \cdot p \cdot q \cdot k^{\lceil \log_k \frac{p}{q} \rceil} \in O(kp^3)$$

states in the new automaton which gives analogous bounds for computation of the minimal $p/q = A/B$.

Conjecture 4. For all odd numbers $p > 1$, $p \neq 23$, there exists an odd number $q < p$ such that $p/q = A/B$ has a solution in palindromes A, B .

We have verified this conjecture for $p < 1000$. For $p = 23$ we can definitively prove, using our automaton method, that there is no odd $q < 23$ such that $p/q = A/B$ has a solution in palindromes.

Sometimes the smallest solution to $p/q = A/B$ can be quite large. For example, the smallest solution to $A/B = 979/765$ in palindromic numbers is

$$\frac{435964577851526887677597179561025269848009167916543881959761365529045212378773108135544954987}{340666907105636434191380840004274087266319727738668099794910566526782009672892163149838499045}.$$

3. Antipalindromic Numbers

In this section we treat the same six problems for the antipalindromic numbers.

3.1. Denseness

Theorem 8. *The set APAL/APAL is dense in the positive reals.*

Proof. The proof is analogous to the proof of Theorem 2. We just outline the basic idea. Let α , β , and k be as in that proof.

There are two cases: k odd and k even.

If k is odd, for a given n define $\gamma = \lfloor 2^n \beta \rfloor$. Set $A = [(\gamma)_2 \overline{(\gamma_2)^R}]_2$ and $B = [10^c 1^c 0]_2$ for $c = n + (k - 1)/2$. Then A and B are both antipalindromic numbers, and A/B is an arbitrarily good approximation to α , as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

If k is even, define $\gamma = \lfloor 2^n / \beta \rfloor$. Set $B = [(\gamma)_2 \overline{(\gamma_2)^R}]_2$ and $A = [10^{n-k/2} 1^{n-k/2} 0]_2$. Then A/B is an arbitrarily good approximation to α , as $n \rightarrow \infty$. \square

Remark 5. Let $a_1 < a_2 < \dots$ be the antipalindromic numbers. Here the criterion of Theorem 1 would not suffice to prove Theorem 8, since $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{n+1}/a_n = 2$.

3.2. Quotients of Antipalindromic Numbers

The set $Q_{\text{apal}} = \{1, 5, 6, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 24, 26, \dots\}$ of integers representable as the quotient of two antipalindromic numbers, forms sequence A351172 in the OEIS. The set $\mathbb{N} - Q_{\text{apal}} = \{2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 22, \dots\}$ of unrepresentable integers forms sequence A351173.

3.2.1. Decision Algorithm

We can verify if a given N is representable as the quotient of antipalindromic numbers A and B using an analogous method to the algorithm given in Section 2.2.3. We build a similar automaton to the automaton in Section 2.2.3, though it interprets the input $\langle a, b \rangle$ as the quotient of $A = a\sigma_a \bar{a}^R$ and $B = b\sigma_b \bar{b}^R$. This interpretation is dependent on the base k , as the middle character must be such that $\sigma = \bar{\sigma}$. If k is odd then, $\sigma_x \in \{\epsilon, (k - 1)/2\}$ and if k is even then $\sigma_x = \epsilon$. When the automaton interprets the input as above and computes accordingly, it accepts antipalindromes that have quotient N . The algorithm also achieves the same asymptotic bounds. Thus we have

Theorem 9. *There is an algorithm that, given a natural number N , can determine if there exist antipalindromes in base k A, B such that $N = A/B$ in $O(k^2 N^3)$ time.*

With our algorithm we computed the number of representable i -bit integers; see Table 5. The available data suggest that perhaps there are roughly $.12 \cdot 1.81^i$ i -bit solutions for i even, and $.36 \cdot 1.81^i$ for i odd.

We can prove the following lower bound.

Theorem 10. *There are $\Omega(2^{i/2})$ i -bit integers representable as the quotient of antipalindromes.*

Proof. If i is odd, then we can get $O(2^{i/2})$ representable integers of i bits by taking A to be an antipalindromic number of $i + 1$ bits, and $B = 2$.

If i is even, say $i = 2j$, we have to work a bit harder. First we observe that if x, y are arbitrary binary strings of j bits and y ends in 1, and $A = [x y \bar{x} \bar{y}]_2$, then A is divisible by $2(2^{2j} - 1)$.

i	$ Q_{\text{apal}} \cap [2^{i-1}, 2^i] $
1	1
2	0
3	2
4	1
5	8
6	4
7	24
8	17
9	75
10	50
11	247
12	165
13	903

Table 5: Number of i -bit numbers representable as the quotient of antipalindromes

To see this, note that

$$\begin{aligned} A &= [x]_2 \cdot 2^{3j} + [y]_2 \cdot 2^{2j} + [\bar{x}]_2 \cdot 2^j + [\bar{y}]_2 \\ &= [x]_2 \cdot 2^{3j} + [y]_2 \cdot 2^{2j} + (2^j - 1 - [x]_2) \cdot 2^j + (2^j - 1 - [y]_2) \\ &= (2^{2j} - 1)([x]_2 \cdot 2^j + [y]_2 + 1), \end{aligned}$$

and observe that the second factor of the last line is even if $[y]_2$ is odd.

Now take $y = x^R$, so that x starts with 1. Then A is an antipalindromic number (because its base-2 representation is given by $x x^R \bar{x} \bar{x}^R$). From the previous paragraph we see that A is divisible by $2(2^{2j} - 1)$. Since $2^{2j} - 1$ is divisible by 3, it follows that A is divisible by the antipalindromic number $B = 2(2^{2j} - 1)/3 = [(10)^j]_2$.

Finally we need to estimate the number of these quotients A/B that have i bits. Suppose $2^{j-1} \leq [x]_2 \leq (2^{j+1} - 5)/3$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{4j-1} &\leq A \leq 2^{3j}(2^{j+1} - 2)/3 \\ \frac{3 \cdot 2^{4j-1}}{2 \cdot (2^{2j} - 1)} &\leq A/B \leq \frac{(2^j - 1)2^{3j}}{2^{2j} - 1} = \frac{2^{3j}}{2^j + 1} < 2^{2j}, \end{aligned}$$

so A/B has $2j$ bits. Thus there are at least

$$(2^{j+1} - 5)/3 - 2^{j-1} + 1 = 2^{j+1}/12 - 2/3$$

numbers of $2j$ bits that are representable as quotients of antipalindromic numbers. \square

Remark 6. Letting $Q_{\text{apal}}(x)$ be the number of integers less than or equal to x in APAL/APAL, we see that the previous result shows $Q_{\text{apal}}(x) = \Omega(x^{1/2})$.

Even the following seems hard to prove.

Conjecture 5. The set of integers representable as quotients of antipalindromic numbers is of zero density.

3.3. Size of the Smallest Representation

With our algorithm, we were able to compute the record-setting values of A, B given in Table 6.

N	A	B
5	10	2
15	150	10
18	936	52
59	52140188	883732
66	65099232	986352
83	206712630902722	2490513625334
343	841469573210301602	2453264061837614
835	180616526119856633856230	216307216910007944738
991	200428779760870700728006297372550	202249020949415439685172853050
1268	75547761517760569279087608058268904	59580253562902657160163728752578
1290	4395923940796125166581803114404301293837667532540	3407692977361337338435506290235892475843153126
1952	1586681992762659022973996447792006955471260017904473853156544	812849381538247450294055557270495366532407796057619801822
4091	102232724919890518755288528068181989159740544137704480818962816	24989666321166100893495118080709359364395146452628814670976
4460	388987104335534771520764071813224655554298718228899978912430000	87216839537115419623489702200274586447152178975089681370500
4640	85112365674283227507265261996365447811182320230460498 83220363630941564530051147747252794193043200	18343182257388626617945099568182208579996189704840624 74831974920461544079752402531735515989880
4848	16307148112492799707206815760673202828585190069605262924 53647949068964670350753495389303768493316355031391840704 83231286976	33636856667683167712885346040992580091966151133674222204 07689663921131745773006384878926915208985880840329704424 1590612
5840	43493875233140378950672024766781801439773086758844870 87734362685028948495519190020221259652712554180379503 2037061443716557960233120	74475813755377361216904151997914043561255285545967244 65298566241487925506026010308598047350535195514348464 389907781458314719218
6624	33301854653004018709445764603598238453897624842252171 14065184395426890419279201949902950413217648251363098 4949626284424060000589698848419903839832345753230313 683200744371137665623242712430446372631626633794372416	50274539029293506505805804051325843076536269387457987 83310966780535764521858698595867980696282681538893566 56849073497016998793160777247010724395882164482533686 11594315273420541307856689678509416158156194715334

Table 6: Record-setters for smallest denominators of solutions A, B to $N = A/B$ in antipalindromes.

The size of smallest solutions is somewhat larger than in the case for palindromes, which is not too surprising, since there are fewer antipalindromes in base 2 than palindromes (since the length of an antipalindrome must be even).

Conjecture 6. Let $A(N)$ be the smallest natural number b such that $N = a/b$ is solvable for antipalindromes a, b , and 0 otherwise. Then $A(N) \neq O(q(N))$ for all polynomials q .

3.4. Numbers Representable as Quotients of Antipalindromes

Theorem 11. *There are infinitely many integers representable as a quotient of antipalindromes in base 2.*

Proof. Integers of the form $N = 2^{2n+1} - 2^n = (1^{n+1}0^n)_2$ are representable as a quotient of antipalindromes. We have that $A/B = N$ for $A = 2^{2n+2} - 2^{n+1} = (1^{n+1}0^{n+1})_2$ and $B = 2 = (10)_2$ which are both antipalindromes. \square

It is easy to see that there are infinitely many integers not representable as a quotient of antipalindromes in base 2, since integers of the form $N = 2^{2n+1}$ are not representable as a quotient of antipalindromes. (There are no antipalindromes of odd length in base 2, as the middle digit σ must satisfy $2 - 1 - \sigma = 1 - \sigma$ which has no solutions in $\{0, 1\}$. Given any antipalindromic B of length $2i$, $N \cdot B$ is of length $2i + 2n + 1$ which is odd and not an antipalindrome. Therefore, there are no antipalindromic A and B such that $A/B = N$.)

However, we can prove a stronger result for antipalindrome quotients:

Theorem 12. *The lower asymptotic density of unrepresentable integers is $\geq 1/60$.*

Proof. We show that if

$$40 \cdot 4^n < N < 48 \cdot 4^n \tag{2}$$

for $n \geq 0$, and $N \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then there is no representation $N = A/B$ for antipalindromes A, B .

Suppose such a representation exists. Notice that A being an antipalindrome implies that $(A)_2$ has an even number of bits; that is, that $2 \cdot 4^i \leq A < 4^{i+1}$ for some i .

Further, the inequality $40 \cdot 4^n < N < 48 \cdot 4^n$ implies that the first three bits of $(N)_2$ must be 101. Since $(B)_2$ is an antipalindrome, B must be even. If $B = 2$, then $N = A/B$ implies that $4^i \leq A < 2 \cdot 4^i$ for some i , contradicting (2).

So B is at least 4, and hence $(B)_2$ has at least three bits. We now claim that the first three bits of $(A)_2$ must be the same as the first three bits of $(B)_2$. To see this, suppose the first three bits of $(B)_2$ are $1bc$. Since $(B)_2$ is an antipalindrome, the last three bits of $(B)_2$ must be $\bar{c}\bar{b}0$. Now $N \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, so by considering $BN \pmod{8}$, we see that the last 3 bits of $A = BN$ must also be $\bar{c}\bar{b}0$. Since $(A)_2$ is an antipalindrome, the first three bits of $(A)_2$ must also be $1bc$, as claimed.

There are now four possibilities to check. These are summarized in Table 7 below, where j is some positive integer.

b	c	inequality
0	0	$(4/5)4^j < A/B < (5/4)4^j$
0	1	$(5/6)4^j < A/B < (6/5)4^j$
1	0	$(6/7)4^j < A/B < (7/6)4^j$
1	1	$(7/8)4^j < A/B < (8/7)4^j$

Table 7: Inequalities.

In each case these contradict (2). So N is not representable.

Thus we have shown that a number N is unrepresentable if it has an even number of bits, is congruent to 1 (mod 4), and begins with 101. If we let $g(x)$ be the number of such numbers less than or equal to x , then $g(x)/x$ clearly has a local minimum at $x = 40 \cdot 4^n$, and for such x we have $g(x) = (2 \cdot 4^n - 2)/3$. The bound of $1/60$ now follows. \square

3.5. Number of Solutions

Another advantage of the finite automaton method is that for a given N we can determine if there are infinitely many solutions to $A/B = N$ in antipalindromes, or whether there are any fixed number of solutions.

Given the finite automaton constructed in Section 3.2.1 for antipalindromes, we first remove all states from which we cannot reach a final state. (The construction ensures that all states are reachable from the start state.) The resulting automaton has a cycle if and only if there are infinitely many solutions.

We used this idea to compute the first few terms of the relevant sets. This gives us sequence A351175, those N for which there are infinitely many solutions:

$$1, 6, 15, 18, 19, 20, 24, 28, 51, 59, 61, 63, 66, 67, 68, 71, 72, 74, \dots,$$

sequence A351176, those N for which there is at least one solution, but only finitely many:

$$5, 17, 21, 26, 65, 69, 70, 85, 89, 92, 102, 106, 116, 219, 221, 233, 239, 245, 249, 257, \dots,$$

and sequence A351325, those N for which there is exactly one solution:

$$5, 21, 26, 69, 85, 89, 92, 102, 106, 116, 219, 221, 233, 239, 245, \dots$$

Theorem 13. *There are infinitely many integers N for which there are infinitely many solutions to the equation $N = A/B$ for antipalindromes A, B .*

Proof. Let $N = 2^{2n+1} - 2^n$ for $n \geq 1$. Define

$$B_i = [1(0^{n+2}1^{n+2})^i 0]_2 = 2^{2ni+4i+1} + (2^{n+2} - 1) \cdot \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 2^{2nj+4j+1}$$

for $i \geq 0$. Clearly B_i is an antipalindrome. We now compute $A_i = N \cdot B_i$.

$$\begin{aligned} N \cdot B_i &= (2^{2n+1} - 2^n) \cdot \left(2^{2ni+4i+1} + (2^{n+2} - 1) \cdot \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 2^{2nj+4j+1} \right) \\ &= (2^{2ni+4i+2n+2} - 2^{2ni+4i+n+1}) + (2^{3n+3} - 2^{2n+2} - 2^{2n+1} + 2^n) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 2^{2nj+4j+1} \right) \\ &= (2^{2ni+4i+2n+2} - 2^{2ni+4i+n+1}) + (2^{2n+3} - 2^{n+2} - 2^{n+1} + 1) \cdot 2^n \cdot \left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 2^{2nj+4j+1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (2^{2ni+4i+2n+2} - 2^{2ni+4i+n+1}) + (2^{2n+3} - 2^{n+2} - 2^{n+1} + 1) \cdot \left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 2^{2nj+4j+n+1} \right) \\
 &= [1^{n+1}0^{2ni+4i+n+1}]_2 + [1^n010^n1]_2 \cdot [(10^{2n+3})^{i-1}10^{n+1}]_2 \\
 &= [1^{n+1}0^{2ni+4i+n+1}]_2 + [(1^n010^n10)^{i-1}1^n010^n10^{n+1}]_2 \\
 &= [1^{n+1}0(1^n010^n10)^{i-1}1^n010^n10^{n+1}]_2 \\
 &= [1^{n+1}(01^n010^n1)^i0^{n+1}]_2 \\
 &= A_i.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus A_i is also an antipalindrome for each $i \geq 0$. Therefore, we have an infinite set of representations $A_i/B_i = N$ where A_i and B_i are antipalindromes for each $N = 2^{2n+1} - 2^n$. \square

Theorem 14. *There are exactly 2^{i-1} solutions to $N = A/B$ for $N = 4^i + 1$ and A, B antipalindromes.*

Proof. Let $N = 4^i + 1 = [10^{2i-1}1]_2$. Consider an antipalindrome B . Let $(B)_k = \beta$ and $|\beta| = \ell$.

If β has length $\ell < 2i$, then $(BN)_k = (A)_k = \beta 0^{2i-\ell} \beta$. Since antipalindromes in base 2 have even length, the center of $(A)_k$ is at least two zeros which means that A is not an antipalindrome.

If β has length $\ell = 2i$, then $(BN)_k = (A)_k = \beta\beta$. Here, A is an antipalindrome since $\overline{(\beta\beta)^R} = \overline{\beta^R\beta^R} = \beta\beta$.

If β has length $\ell > 2i$, then $(BN)_k$ can be viewed as the binary addition of $[\beta 0^{2i}]_2 + [\beta]_2$. Since β was sufficiently long, there is some non-trivial overlap in the addition. Let $j = 2i - \ell$. The overlap has length $\ell - j$ and there are j symbols of β on each side of the overlap.

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \beta[1 : j] \quad | \quad \beta[j+1 : \ell] \quad | \quad 0^j \\
 + \quad 0^j \quad | \quad \beta[1 : \ell-j] \quad | \quad \beta[\ell-j+1 : \ell]
 \end{array}$$

Figure 1: Piecewise addition of $[\beta 0^{2i}]_2 + [\beta]_2$.

Since B is an antipalindrome, we get that $\beta[1 : j] = \overline{\beta[\ell-j+1 : \ell]^R}$. This means that for $[\beta 0^{2i}]_2 + [\beta]_2$ to be an antipalindrome the overlap region must not overflow to the left. We have additional information that further constrains this addition. We know that $\beta[1] = 1$ which implies that $\beta[\ell] = \overline{\beta[1]} = 0$. Additionally, we know that the overlap region cannot overflow so $\beta[j+1] = 0$ which subsequently implies that $\beta[\ell-j] = \overline{\beta[j+1]} = 1$. As well, the remaining addition $\beta[j+2 : \ell-1] + \beta[2 : \ell-j-1]$ must not overflow either.

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \beta[1:j] \mid 0 \mid \beta[j+2:\ell-1] \mid 0 \mid 0^j \\
 + \quad 0^j \mid 1 \mid \beta[2:\ell-j-1] \mid 1 \mid \beta[\ell-j+1:\ell] \\
 \hline
 = \beta[1:j] \mid 1 \mid \beta' \mid 1 \mid \beta[\ell-j+1:\ell]
 \end{array}$$

Figure 2: Piecewise addition of $[\beta 0^{2i}]_2 + [\beta]_2$ with constraints.

From the result of the addition we see that we have a 1 at $j + 1$ symbols from the front and a 1 at $j + 1$ symbols from the back. Therefore, this cannot be an antipalindrome.

Overall, given an antipalindrome B , BN is an antipalindrome if and only if $(B)_k$ has length $2i$. There are 2^{i-1} antipalindromes of length $2i$, so for $N = 4^i + 1$ there are exactly 2^{i-1} solutions to $N = A/B$ for A and B antipalindromes. \square

Theorem 15. *There are infinitely many integers N such that $N = A/B$ has exactly one solution in antipalindromes A, B .*

Proof. Consider N of the form $(2^{2n} - 1)/3$ for $n \geq 2$. Clearly $(2N)_2 = (10)^n$, so $2N$ and 2 are both antipalindromes. This gives one solution to $N = A/B$.

Now let us assume there is another solution to $N = A/B$ with A, B antipalindromes. Since $B > 2$, and the next larger antipalindrome is 10 , we see that B has at least 4 bits. Choose $k \geq 1$ such that $4 \cdot 2^k \leq B < 8 \cdot 2^k$.

Note that $5 \cdot 2^{2n-3} \leq N < (16/3) \cdot 2^{2n-3}$. We can use this inequality together with $A = BN$ to determine the first three bits of A . They are summarized in Table 8, where $\ell = k + 2n - 3$.

first three bits of B	inequality for B	inequality for $A = BN$	first three bits of $A = BN$
100	$4 \cdot 2^k \leq B < 5 \cdot 2^k$	$20 \cdot 2^\ell \leq A < \frac{80}{3} \cdot 2^\ell$	101 or 110
101	$5 \cdot 2^k \leq B < 6 \cdot 2^k$	$25 \cdot 2^\ell \leq A < 32 \cdot 2^\ell$	110 or 111
110	$6 \cdot 2^k \leq B < 7 \cdot 2^k$	$30 \cdot 2^\ell \leq A < \frac{112}{3} \cdot 2^\ell$	111 or 100
111	$7 \cdot 2^k \leq B < 8 \cdot 2^k$	$35 \cdot 2^\ell \leq A < \frac{128}{3} \cdot 2^\ell$	100 or 101

Table 8: Possibilities for first three bits of A .

On the other hand, if B starts with three bits abc , then since B is an antipalindrome, it must end with $\overline{c\overline{b}\overline{a}}$. Since $N \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$, one can easily check that $A = BN$ also ends with $\overline{c\overline{b}\overline{a}}$. Since A is an antipalindrome, it must begin with abc . So the first three bits of A and B are the same. This contradicts the results of Table 8, and proves there are no other solutions. \square

3.6. Rational Solutions to $p/q = A/B$ in Antipalindromes

Once again our automaton method for antipalindromes can be generalized to give the following result.

Theorem 16. *There is an algorithm that, given integers $p, q \geq 1$, decides whether there is a solution to $p/q = A/B$ in antipalindromes A, B .*

We used our algorithm to study the rational solutions to $p/q = A/B$ in antipalindromes for $p > q$ and $p \leq 1000$. Based on our calculations, we make the following conjecture.

Conjecture 7. For all $p \geq 4$ there exists $q < p$ such that $p/q = A/B$ has a solution in antipalindromes.

We note that there are no solutions for $(p, q) \in \{(2, 1), (3, 1), (3, 2)\}$.

Some solutions to $p/q = A/B$ can be enormously large. For example, the smallest solution for $p/q = 960/527$ is $A =$

```

1234883355213990975204467140683475994799335003626682427756930130658317
0577845541101597875372665385744362733254798839009872167396310323997903
5640547077917392804795250182028753800174169116477800361082899344465944
5560841114705454770902394470289417027557405950223685182751710075724367
6048238590480983878073501486368624181821560779594741108091349800844282
5679592833678865846036391335428845975712764583827139150178213891564696
4718825426930262288729775928481863474655184300859716583115484263497126
2961706100246193708891656878945533178186000927736300244493837237642640
9349549969820438753161560915890436797199051312068851515357512387981254
4604809069807177738058155380014435541831993909182136704602824634226568
3451444571619483682225669077170879824401082095216563292486986361198314
2620371328966957512364597567158981492432747694245025717455343991855418
3265938974040814493629275353847375559776274838299843008368743842579023
9993356699741468657156369097163207591351729526813712761138142291367822
0794954727600533534516312312331038829749723349859042215544591191317981
8600650852792742320291709382397741664309047654075764338087057307850282
7509649077719055308633225064218430763198619435136533732460140152765958
4251780426995592541451396343086191791838699791485099128013340230974422
4295888043536875650860208149665479650685364073997568860181548161096442
1040420056468998183952438585617409445628800
    
```

and $B =$

6778995085393471290966189407710331763117182780325642077373981029759719
 6817964585005646670014527690492491254429989459981277418935995216113491
 4401753229817354251323925478428679715539449212331258232194666193057841
 4693367369268486086099602977526278890862009747582105117814075103195226
 3306476428994567747340992534544426498124609696316964207959805677551426
 1803598159882940633970606601781269054173197246634399293165820008902031
 6737718749919252355839499107395229699409188818261152492727710488156099
 5633532446143167547769824741711416509416900926219064883835960669142414
 2991800355160116905376485444523543667957292098544632797848010713188761
 4653483122795652791215082138204245109848549897281104617975922731639599
 1446992596286123963884662538219309036035106918532592241048352211994912
 6676413441308193843918155394716492151167271196532589094780898788622973
 5220310826244887897319042827891322083355175414416846514690916719157767
 1630197716289103982514651189635525006691265214904444011664593620321273
 2905636890057095548855172797900598575813585472663700495749995394006004
 5859822910643491695768029630454269344696542851020081314290408346219781
 3516511082895230704684475092115760543809087940801596635484311046954792
 6048836302361221555675894508400240357281195730340075421489898976286673
 1290968738999306958368017654934455999074863197882487388704957092685676
 966980593499127128065557431896223726923310 .

4. Going Further

We have not examined what surprises might await us in other bases. To give just a taste, the smallest representation of 436 as the quotient of base-10 palindromes is

$$\frac{4062320931846767973606063797676481390232604}{9317249843685247645885467425863489427139} .$$

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